

SCREENING STUDIES OF RETINOPATHY OF PREMATURITY AND ITS PROSPECTS FOR OPHTHALMOLOGY

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Abstract: Our studies established that the maturation of biochemical autoregulation of retinal vessels began from the 30th week of postconceptual age [7]. The causes of delayed maturation of vascular autoregulation have been identified. In the majority of children (70–80%), adaptation to new living conditions was successful, but in every 3–4th child, failure of autoregulation of retinal vessels was detected and ROP developed. We noted that the maturation of vascular autoregulation is delayed not only by gestational age, but also by concomitant diseases. These include severe forms of respiratory distress syndrome, anemia, neonatal sepsis, thrombocytopenia, multiple blood transfusions, apnea, and intraventricular hemorrhages.

Inappropriate vasospasm. The lower the degree of maturity of the child, the more often retinal arteriospasm is detected. In those born at 25–27 weeks, arteriospasm was detected in 82% of cases, at 28–29 weeks – in 67%, at 30–32 weeks – in 54% of cases.

For the development of ROP, it is not so much vasospasm that is important as its degree, i.e. the degree of obstruction of blood flow caused by vasospasm. We assessed hemodynamics in the anterior cerebral artery and in the ophthalmic artery using the resistance index. An index of cerebral and ocular vascular resistance of 0.8 or higher is threatening for the development of ROP in a child. The resistance index, a routine method for studying the vessels of the brain and eye, makes it possible to monitor the degree of vasospasm even when it is impossible to perform ophthalmoscopy (opacity of the optical media, seclusion of the pupil, etc.). It is enough to study the cerebral vascular resistance index to determine the threat of development.

Key words: screening for retinopathy of prematurity, autoregulation of retinal vessels, inadequate vasospasm, oxygen therapy, gestational age.

Introduction. Retinopathy of prematurity (ROP) is a leading cause of blindness in premature infants and a complex problem. To date, issues with its diagnosis, treatment and prevention have not been resolved. A large number of risk factors for the development of ROP have been developed, but their information content does not satisfy the needs of the clinic. Most ophthalmologists focus on the active or scar phase of ROP. However, the preclinical phase, which lasts about one month, attracts virtually no attention. This phase of RN is studied in Russia by only two scientific schools of pediatric ophthalmologists: the school of corresponding member. RAS, professor E.I. Sidorenko (Department of Ophthalmology, Pediatric Faculty, Federal State Autonomous Educational Institution of Higher Education, Russian National Research Medical University named after N.I. Pirogov) and the school of Professor L.A. Katargina (Federal State Budgetary Institution Helmholtz National Medical Research Center, Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation). During the first month of a child's life, ophthalmologists often take a wait-and-see approach and do not provide treatment, although at this time serious morphofunctional changes occur in the eye. Work in this

preclinical phase is critical in the prevention of ROP and blindness. We propose to distinguish the first preclinical phase in the classification of ROP, which includes the phase of delayed vascular growth. In the course of research at the Department of Ophthalmology, Faculty of Pediatrics, SamSMU, the basis of the first preclinical phase of ROP was revealed and an explanation was obtained for why vascular growth is delayed in this case [1–4, 6–13]. Based on the above, it is necessary to radically reconsider the tactics of diagnosing and treating ROP. In this case, the main attention should be paid to the preclinical stage, which will make it possible to detect ROP early and begin treatment.

To date, unfortunately, screening informative research schemes have not been developed, and the most significant predictors (from English: predictor, prognostic parameter, forecasting tool, corrector, prognostic factor, extrapolator) of the development of ROP have not been identified.

We believe that domestic ophthalmologists need to actively participate in the development of screening examination standards, which will reduce the frequency of RP, identify it as early as possible and provide optimal treatment.

What is screening? For most researchers, it is the process of identifying disease in apparently healthy people at risk by using simple, safe, reproducible, sensitive and valid tests.

It must be admitted that attempts are being made to predict PH using various neonatal assessment scales. To do this, it is proposed to use the Infant Clinical Risk Score, the Neonatal Acute Physiology (SNAP) score, and the SNAP-II Perinatal Extension [11]. However, none of the above scales has sufficient accuracy to predict severe ROP.

Today, there is a need to improve existing screening protocols by developing new, better predictors in order to reduce the number of screening procedures for pH and increase their information content [20].

In domestic and International literature has paid much attention to the leading risk factors for the development of ROP: small gestational age (less than 35 weeks of the child's postconceptional age) and body weight (BW) less than 1500 g at birth.

Gestational age. The lower the gestational age, the greater the underdevelopment of organs and systems. At gestational age 28 weeks. ROP occurs in 81.8% of cases, 32 weeks. – in 56%, 34 weeks. – in 14% of cases. The critical gestational age in different countries ranges from 28 to 31–34 weeks. The smaller it is (very premature babies), the more often it is necessary to examine the child, even at 2–3 weeks after birth and earlier. A number of authors indicate that in newborns with small gestational age, ROP develops only in 19–47% of cases, and only 10% of children require treatment [15]. The threshold stage of ROP was reached in 5.2–16.1% of cases (Shah P.K. et al., 2016, Good W.V., 2005, Sidorenko E.I., 2009, Katargina L.A., 2016) and required laser intervention (Holmström G., 2016, Astasheva I.B., 2014).

In the course of research at the Department of Ophthalmology, Faculty of Pediatrics, SamSMU, the essence of this factor was revealed [1, 4, 7]. Gestational age reflects not so much the passport age as the degree of maturity of the body systems that maintain the homeostasis of the premature baby in new living conditions with excess oxygen postpartum. The main problem of the early postpartum period is poor protection of retinal tissue from oxygen, since immature biochemical autoregulation of retinal vessels does not work adequately.

Purpose of the study. Identify retinopathy of prematurity in the early stages.

Materials and methods of research. Our studies established that the maturation of biochemical autoregulation of retinal vessels began from the 30th week of postconceptual age [7]. The causes of delayed maturation of vascular autoregulation have been identified. In the majority of children (70–80%), adaptation to new living conditions was successful, but in every 3–4th child, failure of autoregulation of retinal vessels

was detected and ROP developed. We noted that the maturation of vascular autoregulation is delayed not only by gestational age, but also by concomitant diseases. These include severe forms of respiratory distress syndrome, anemia, neonatal sepsis, thrombocytopenia, multiple blood transfusions, apnea, and intraventricular hemorrhages.

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The second factor indicating the possibility of developing ROP and the threat of blindness in a premature infant is his birth weight. The correlation between the child's body weight at birth and the caliber of blood vessels is 2 times weaker than gestational age.

At a birth weight of 1000 g, ROP develops in 83% of cases, at 1250 g – in 70%, at 1500 g – in 45%, at 1750 g – in 29%, at 2000 g – in 15%, at 2250 g - in 10% of cases (Nikolaeva G.V., 2007–2017).

In the UK, all babies born before 31 weeks. or with a body weight of up to 1500 g, undergo screening studies. In this group of children, stage III ROP is observed in 8–10% of cases. In the United States, infants with a birth weight between 1500 and 2000 or those born at more than 30 weeks' gestation but with clinical complications after birth are eligible for PH screening.

Thus, infants with a gestational age of up to 34 weeks are at risk for developing ROP. (up to 32 weeks in Western Europe, USA, Japan), with a birth weight of up to 2250 g (up to 1500 g in Western Europe, USA, Japan).

In many developing countries, children born at 34–36 weeks' gestation. or with a birth weight between 1750 and 2000 g are screened if the neonatal period was complicated. Pediatricians should carefully consider this risk factor. Children born before the 28th week or with a birth weight of less than 1200 g should be screened somewhat earlier, at 2–3 weeks after birth [12].

Screening guidelines use only the two most important risk factors: gestational age and birth weight. However, only 10% of screened preterm infants require treatment [15].

Dynamics of newborn body weight

Binenbaum et al. [16] found that the birth weight-gestational age-weight gain model could improve disease prognosis and reduce screening by 30% in high-risk populations, identifying children in need of laser therapy.

It should be taken into account that an important prognostic sign of the development of ROP is the study of the dynamics of the newborn's body weight in the first 6 weeks. after birth (the Winrop algorithm is approved in many countries and its sensitivity ranges from 85 to 100%). Body weight must be determined weekly. Its increase by the 6th week is estimated using the formula: the difference between body weight at the 6th week and BW at the time of birth, divided by body weight at birth. Body weight gain less than 50% during the first 6 weeks. life is superior in predictive value of birth weight and gestational age separately as predictors of severe ROP.

Long-term oxygen therapy. Retinopathy of prematurity usually develops in infants weighing less than 1500 g and less than 30 weeks of age. gestation at birth, particularly in those with serious complications or who have received excessive or prolonged oxygen therapy. Risk factors for prematurity include oxygen inhalation for more than 20–50 days, artificial ventilation for more than 5–7 days, and stay in an incubator for more than 4 weeks.

Screening scales for prognostic research in premature infants

S. Lofqvist et al. [23, 24] developed the WINROP algorithm to detect the development of severe ROP among preterm infants. This algorithm is based on weekly determination of BW and the level of insulin-like growth factor (IGF-1) in the blood serum from the moment of birth to the age of 36 weeks. after conception. The authors examined 50 premature newborns. The sensitivity of the developed algorithm is determined to be in the range of 85 to 100%, and it is validated as a convenient screening tool for pH. The WINROP algorithm is currently being tested in a large multicenter, multinational study. G.U. Eckert et al. [13] analyzed 16 variables in the ROPScore. The pH ROPScore is based on indicators such as BW at birth, BW gain and blood transfusions from birth to 6 weeks of life, and oxygen use. The study included 474 patients. The authors assessed this score as a promising tool with greater predictive value than BW and gestational age at birth.

Laboratory research methods. Very informative are laboratory methods for studying the system that fights circulatory hypoxia, the failure of which is caused, according to the concept of E.I. Sidorenko pathological angiogenesis. In the works of N.V. Fomina, N.A. Osipova, this is well demonstrated in the works of foreign authors.

A. Perez-Munuzuri et al. [2] and N.V. Fomina [16], having conducted a study using the WINROP algorithm, concluded that determination of serum levels of IGF-1 at 3 weeks after birth serves as a satisfactory prognostic tool for identifying infants at high risk of developing ROP. IGF plays an important role in fetal development during pregnancy. IGF-1 levels increase significantly during the third trimester of pregnancy, they control retinal vascular growth factor (VEGF or VEGF). However, IGF-1 levels decline rapidly after preterm birth. An extended period of low IGF-1 levels in preterm infants is associated with the development of ROP.

N.A. Osipova [5] identified prognostically unfavorable laboratory criteria, the level of which reflects the critical moments of the onset of the active clinical phase of ROP: serum concentration of VEGF-A - above 1300 pg/ml, IGF-I - below 24 pg/mg, IGF-II - above 140 pg /ml, TGF- β – below 8000 pg/ml. S. Pieh et al. [11] found an association between increased levels of plasma soluble E-selectin (sE-selectin) and pH. The authors believe that taking into account the gestational age of the newborn and the level of sE-selectin in the blood plasma improves the ability to predict PH. Thus, an increase in sE-selectin to 10 ng/ml 2–3 weeks after birth increases the risk of developing ROP by 1.6 times. Study of granulocyte colony-stimulating factor. R. Bhola et al. [13] conducted a retrospective review of 213 neonates receiving G-CSF for non-ophthalmic indications. From this group, 50 newborns with BW at birth <1500 g and gestational age at birth <32 weeks were examined. Retinopathy of prematurity requiring laser therapy was noted in only 10% of infants receiving G-CSF, and in the control group - in 18.6%. Another retrospective study measured the levels of 27 types of cytokines in the vitreous of eyes with pH and the levels of 6 cytokines, including granulocyte colony-stimulating factor (G-CSF). It was found that their content was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in eyes with PH than in the control group. In an animal study with oxygen-induced retinopathy , the level of G-CSF significantly reduced the severity of vascular obliteration ($p < 0.01$) and neovascularization ($p < 0.01$), mainly due to increased levels of IGF-1 [20]. The results of these studies suggest a potential role for G-CSF in the prevention of ROP, but further research is needed. N.V. Fomina highly appreciates laboratory tests and points out that they are still very expensive, labor-intensive, time-

consuming and cannot yet be used as screening tests in clinical practice. Therefore, this work must be continued.

Conclusions. Thus, the above facts indicate that screening systems for predicting ROP in Uzbekistan have not currently been developed, however, they provide:

- 1) the possibility of a more thorough study of the very early signs of the preclinical stage of ROP;
- 2) chances to save obstetricians, neonatologists and resuscitators from mistakes;
- 3) encouraging neonatologists to take a more active role in the prevention of blindness from ROP, providing them with non-ophthalmological signs that will be easier for them to work with;
- 4) relieve premature babies from frequent examinations by an ophthalmologist, which are quite a burden for them and can cause injury and cause disruption of internal organs, including cardiac arrest;
- 5) relieve the ophthalmologist from unreasonable calls, reducing his medical workload;
- 6) encourage the development of new methods for the prevention and treatment of ROP.

Taking into account the above, we propose a new screening scheme, where physician researchers must control 4 functions: 1) gestational age; 2) dynamics of the cerebral vascular resistance index; 3) body weight at birth; 4) dynamics of body weight over 6 weeks.

The critical gestational age in different countries ranges from 28 to 31–34 weeks.

When the vascular resistance index of the brain and eye increases to 0.8 or more, consultation with an ophthalmologist is required, since there is a threat of developing ROP.

Body weight at birth. Only approximately 10% of preterm infants screened for BW require treatment. BW control is 1.6 times less informative than gestational age. Larger newborns born at 34–36 weeks gestation, or with a birth weight between 1750 and 2250 g should be screened if the neonatal period was complicated.

Dynamics of body weight over 6 weeks. In a very premature baby it is necessary to determine it weekly. The increase in BW by the 6th week is calculated using the formula: the difference between BW at the 6th week and BW at the time of birth, divided by BW at birth.

Body weight gain less than 50% during the first 6 weeks. life is superior in prognostic value to BW and gestational age separately as predictors of severe.

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